

Tris-(2,2'-dipyridyl) Complex of Trivalent Rhenium

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In a previous communication¹, the preparation and the properties of cationic and non-electrolytic complexes of Re (v) and Re (iv) with 2,2'-dipyridyl have been described. It has now been possible to isolate the tris-(2,2'-dipyridyl) complex of Re(III). Analogous 1,10-phenanthroline complex has been reported previously².

An intimate mixture of 2,2'-dipyridylum hexachlororhenate (iv), $(\text{dipyH})_6[\text{ReCl}_6]$, and excess (5 moles) of 2,2'-dipyridyl was heated in a sealed tube for 1 hr. at 240°. The cooled mass was washed with benzene and extracted with ethanol, leaving a yellow residue of $[\text{Re}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_4]$. From the blue-violet ethanol extract a violet substance was precipitated with ether. This was dissolved in ethanol and reprecipitated with ether. The process was repeated several times to obtain the intense violet $[\text{Re}(\text{dipy})_3]\text{Cl}_3$ in microcrystalline form. The yield of the substance is very poor.

Tris-dipyridylrhenium (III) chloride is highly soluble in water, ethanol, and acetone, forming an intense blue-violet solution. The trivalency of rhenium in the compound has been proved by dichromate oxidation. The chloride is unstable. In solution and also in the solid state it slowly decomposes to the violet $[\text{ReO}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_2]$. With acids the solution develops a violet colour. The perchlorate, $[\text{Re}(\text{dipy})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_3$, has been isolated as violet microcrystals by metathesis of the chloride and sodium perchlorate solution. It is less soluble in water, but soluble in ethanol and acetone. It is stable in the solid state and also in solution. $[\text{Re}(\text{dipy})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_3$ is weakly paramagnetic, the magnetic moment, corrected for dipyrldyl and perchlorate groups, being 1.0 B.M. at 27°. An aqueous solution of the tris-dipyridylrhenium(III) perchlorate absorbs strongly in the visible and in the UV region. The absorption spectra of a $2.6 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution show two fairly sharp peaks at 236 m μ (log ϵ , 4.57) and at 288 m μ (log ϵ , 4.58) and a very broad band around the region of 590 m μ (log ϵ , 3.88).

The resolution of $[\text{Re}(\text{dipy})_3]^{3+}$ into its possible optical isomers is in progress. Details of the work will be published later on.

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1. Chakravorti, this *Journal*, 1965, 42, 503.

2. Sen *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1963, 40, 707.